

Impact of “Do It” Creativity and Emotional Mastery Strategies on Creativity and Motivation among Adolescents with Special Needs in Oyo State

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Abstract

The study investigated impact of “DO IT” creativity and emotional mastery strategies in fostering creativity motivation among adolescents with special needs in Oyo State. Ninety participants were randomly selected from three special institutions: Cheshire High School, Ibadan; Rehabilitation Centre for the Disabled, Ibadan; and Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. The age range of the participants was between 13 and 21 with a mean age of 18.5 years. The Self Concept Scale of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory APDI) was used to classify the participants into self-concept categories ($r = .80$). The criterion measure was Creativity Motivation Scale of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory ($r = 0.77$). One major hypothesis, with a sub-hypothesis, was generated for the study. Results showed that Creativity Motivation Scores of participants in the “DO IT” and Emotional Mastery groups improved significantly over their counterparts in the control group. It also found that participants in the “DO IT” group benefited more from the programme than those in the Emotional Mastery group. On this that basis, it was recommended that a combination of “DO IT” and creativity and emotional mastery strategies be employed for higher productivity among adolescents with special needs.

Keywords: “DO IT” Creativity, Emotional Mastery, Creativity Motivation, Adolescents with Special Needs

Introduction

The need for creativity motivation is most acute in this generation more than ever. At personal level, it is meant to solve problems in daily life. At societal level, it brings about new findings, new inventions and new social programmes to ease and accelerate man’s comfort, satisfaction, progress and development. All these cannot be realized in the absence of creativity propelled by human motivation and curiosity leading to goal-attainment, self-esteem, self-actualization and comfort.

Smith, Pickering and Bhattacharya (2022) noted that creativity motivation is a multifaceted psychological construct, often fueled by a combination of internal and external motivational factors. One significant factor in creativity is intrinsic motivation, which refers to the desire to engage in an activity for its own sake, rather than for external rewards (Pascale and Woodman, 2016). Amabile (1996) emphasized the role of intrinsic motivation in fostering creativity, arguing that individuals are most creative when they are motivated by the interest, enjoyment, and personal challenge of the task at hand, rather than by external pressures or rewards. This intrinsic drive allows for deeper engagement with the task and fosters risk-taking, exploration, and innovation.

However, external factors, or extrinsic motivation, also play a role in creativity, albeit in more complex ways. While some studies suggest that extrinsic rewards, such as monetary incentives, can stifle creativity by narrowing the focus to obtaining the reward (Deci, Koestner & Ryan, 1999), other research indicates that certain types of extrinsic motivation, like recognition or constructive feedback, can enhance creative performance if they are perceived as supporting the individual's autonomy and competence (Ryan & Deci, 2000). This suggests that the relationship between extrinsic motivation and creativity is nuanced, and the impact of external factors depends largely on how they are perceived by the individual.

Recent models of creativity motivation suggest the importance of a dual emotional pathway to creativity. According to Baas, De Dreu, and Nijstad (2008), both positive and negative emotions can stimulate creativity, albeit through different mechanisms. Positive emotions tend to broaden cognitive processes, leading to more diverse and flexible thinking, while negative emotions, when they trigger task engagement and focus, can encourage deeper problem-solving. Thus, emotional motivation—whether positive or negative—can serve as a potent catalyst for creative thinking, depending on the emotional context and individual interpretation. Often, creativity is influenced by the environment in which individuals operate. A supportive environment that provides opportunities for exploration, collaboration, and experimentation can significantly enhance creativity. Pascale and Woodman (2016), Simonton (2019), Plucker, Makel and Qian (2019) and Smith, Pickering, Bhattacharya (2022) argue that environments promoting psychological safety and diversity of thought are critical for creative breakthroughs, as they allow individuals to take risks without fear of failure.

It has also been established that positive emotions, such as joy and curiosity, are known to facilitate creative thinking by broadening cognitive flexibility (Fredrickson, 2001). Conversely, stress or negative emotions may either inhibit creativity or, in some cases, motivate individuals to engage in problem-solving under pressure. The dual pathway model proposed by De Dreu, Baas and Nijstad (2008) suggest that different emotional states can activate distinct cognitive pathways leading to creative outcomes.

The social and cultural environment plays a crucial role in shaping creative motivation. Societies that value innovation, diversity, and unconventional thinking tend to produce more creative individuals. Cultural norms, social support systems, and the availability of resources all contribute to whether creativity is fostered or stifled (Csikszentmihalyi, 2013). Ultimately, creativity is a dynamic interplay between intrinsic motivation, the structuring of extrinsic factors, and emotional influences. This complexity underlines the importance of considering multiple motivational pathways to understand how creativity can be nurtured in various settings.

Akinboye (2003) opined that creativity is the bedrock of human success as well as the quality of individual, family and organizational prosperity and well-being. Etuk (1992) explained that the days are gone when life was simple as against nowadays when there are many problems, challenges, ambiguities and situations that are neither structured nor well-defined, hence the need for creative thinking and ideas.

De Bono (1971) defined creativity as bringing out new ideas and updating old ones. Animasahun (2002) defined creativity as conscious cognitive processes stimulated by problematic situation, guided by interest and resulting in the generation of statistically infrequent, novel, original, unique, valuable and appropriate ideas useful in turning challenges of life into fruitful, benefited and profitable outcomes. Olawale (2007) submitted that creativity is thinking new ideas and doing new things for the satisfaction and development of self and society. Akinboye and Olawale (2005) defined “DO IT” creativity as follows:

D – Define (the problem).

O – Open (yourself to many possible solutions),

I – Identify (the best of the many possible solutions).

T – Transform (the best solution into effective action).

Besides, Pool (1997) established that emotional well-being is a predictor of success in academic achievement and job success among others. Click (2002) noted emotional intelligence distinguished individual “star performers” and plays an important role in determining which organizations will out-perform others in competitions. Akinboye (2003) corroborated this when he declared that emotional intelligence is the basis for good character, trust, integrity, resilience, commitment, motivation, sensitivity, humour, courage, conscience and humility. Goleman (1998) showed that when cognitive intelligence provides entry into a particular career, it is emotional intelligence that determines how successful someone would be afterwards.

Therefore, it is necessary to subject the afore-mentioned two novel techniques (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) to experimental manipulation to foster creativity motivation thereby since both methods have the capacity to do that. For instance, Akinboye (1976b), Owolabi (1988), Olagunju (1990) and Animasahun (2002) have shown that creativity motivation could be deliberately fostered. This study would provide empirical evidence as regards the comparative effects of the two techniques on the subjects in order to verify the earlier studies.

In most cases, the inherent or acquired disability makes it difficult for individual persons to be motivated to use their initiatives, or become creative not to talk of living independently. This makes people with special needs resort to fate and become burden on the family and society in addition to self-pity. If the situation continues, the adolescents concerned and the society may not be able to cope with the emerging personal, social, economic and security

challenges. Therefore, it is necessary to foster creativity motivation in adolescents with special needs so that they would be able to think and act creatively and stand on their own.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study essentially is to experimentally investigate the impact of “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery Strategies in fostering creativity motivation among selected adolescents with special needs in Oyo State.

Research Question

One Research Question for the study is stated below.

Will there be a significant difference in the creativity motivation scores of treated participants and participants in the control group; and will the two treatment strategies have equal effects on the treated participants.

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis at .05 degree of significance is stated below.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the creativity motivation scores of treated participants and participants in the control group; and the two treatment strategies have equal effects on the treated participants.

Design of the Study

A 3 x 3 factorial design is adopted for the study. The two experimental and control groups form the rows while three levels of self-concept (low, moderate and high) constitute the columns. The design has the capacity of revealing the effectiveness of the two treatments (training programmes) and mediating the extraneous factors. The use of control will actually consolidate the results.

Participants

Ninety (90) adolescents with special needs were randomly selected from three special institutions in Oyo State. They were: Cheshire High School, Ibadan; Rehabilitation Centre for the Disabled, Moniya, and; Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. Their age ranged between 13 and 21 with a mean age of 18.5 years. The participants were matched into different categories of self-concept on the basis of their scores in the Self-Concept Scale of the Adolescent Personal Data Inventory (APDI), whereas they were assigned into treatment and control groups on the basis of balloting.

Instrumentation

There were two standardized instruments adopted for the study. The first was the 30-item Section A of APDI by Akinboye (1977a) to determine the self-concept level of the participants ($r = .80$). The second was the 17-item Section D of APDI to measure the Creativity Motivation of the participants ($r = .77$).

Procedure

The first meeting with the participants in the institutions targeted on general introduction, establishment of rapport and administration of APDI (Self-Concept Scale) for the purpose of assigning them to appropriate Self-Concept levels. After this, they balloted for the three groups (experimental groups and control). The first meeting ended with collection of pre-test data of the groups. Then, the “DO IT” group was exposed to creativity motivation programme for six weeks (one hour per week). Likewise, the Emotional Mastery group was exposed to emotional mastery package for six weeks (one hour per week), whereas the control group was not exposed to any form of training programme. At the end of the exercise, the same (but fresh) instruments were administered on the participants to collect post-test data.

Data analysis

The study employed Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and t-test to analyze the data collected.

Results

The hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the Creativity Motivation Scores of treated participants and participants in the control group; and the two treatment strategies have equal effects on the treated participants.

Tables 1 - 3 resent the data to test this hypothesis. In testing this hypothesis, a Regression Analysis of Creativity Motivation Scores using pre-test as Covariates was carried out. The resultant unadjusted Y-means for Creativity Motivation are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Mean Scores on Creativity Motivation

GROUPS	Improved Creativity Motivation Variable								
	Low Self Concept (LSC)			Moderate Self Concept (MSC)			High Self Concept (HSC)		
	X- \bar{X}	N	Y- \bar{Y}	X- \bar{X}	N	Y- \bar{Y}	X- \bar{X}	N	Y- \bar{Y}
“DO IT”	33.40	10	61.40	40.90	10	71.50	46.50	10	72.10
Emotional Mastery	34.90	10	53.90	41.60	10	62.30	47.20	10	66.00
CONTROL	51.70	10	36.10	57.70	10	40.20	69.50	10	49.30

Source: Field Study by the Researchers

Table 1 shows that the unadjusted Y-means scores of treated groups (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) and the Control group. Treated groups seemed to perform better than the control group. This shows that the treatment strategies accounted for the higher scores than those in the control group. However, the participants in the “DO IT” group performed better than those in the Emotional Mastery group. For further clarity and explanation of the hypothesis, an analysis of covariance was performed to determine whether there was a significant difference in the creativity motivation of treated participants and participants in the control group. The results are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance for Creativity Motivation Variable.

Source of variation	Sums of squares	DF	Mean Squares	F	P
ROWS	1279.298	2	639.649	98.28	<0.01
COLUMNS	176.028	2	88.014	13.52	<0.01
INTERACTION	17.513	4	4.378	0.67	NS
WITHIN	5271.593	81	6.508		

Source: Field Study by the Researchers

Table 2 describes Analysis of Covariance on Creativity Motivation variable of the two treatment groups (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) and the Control Group. The Rows comprise of the treatment groups and the control group. The columns consist of the three levels of self-concept (Low, Moderate and High). The interaction shows the relationship between the rows and the columns. From the foregoing, it is clear that there is a significant difference in the performances of the treated groups and the control as shown in the rows ($F = 98.28$, $df=2/81$ $p<0.01$). This shows that the treated groups benefited greatly from the treatments than the control group. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected. There is also a significant difference in the level of self-concept of the participants as indicated by columns ($F=13.52$, $df^2/81$, $p<0.01$). However, there was no significant difference in the interaction ($F=0.67$, $df = 4/81$, (NS).

In order to show clearly the results for easy comparison, the table for the adjusted Y-means for the treated groups and control group on creativity motivation variable was constructed as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Adjusted Y – Mean Scores on Creativity Motivation Variable

GROUP	Low Self Concept (LSC)	Moderate Self Concept (MSC)	High Self Concept (HSC)
“DO IT”	(a) 62.65	(b) 72.06	(c) 72.15
Emotional Mastery	(d) 55.01	(e) 62.80	(f) 65.99
CONTROL	(g) 35.67	(h) 39.22	(i) 47.24

Source: Field Study by the Researchers

Table 3 presents the adjusted Y-mean scores of the treated participants (“DO IT” and Emotional Mastery) and the participants in the Control on Creativity Motivation Variable. From the table, it is clear that the scores of the treated subjects ($X=62.65$, 72.06 , 72.15 , 55.01 , 62.80 and 65.99) were higher than the scores of participants in the control group ($X=35.67$, 39.22 and 47.24). This shows that the treated groups benefited highly from the treatment programmes than those in the control group. However, those in the “DO IT” group benefited more than those in the Emotional Mastery group.

For a comprehensive analysis of the results and to ascertain the extent of difference that existed, Scheffe post

hoc analysis showing series of t-tests were computed to determine the difference in the mean using the adjusted Y-mean scores and the variance of the mean. See Appendix K for the pair comparisons and their description.

In the final analysis, there was significant difference in the Creativity Motivation scores of participants in the treated groups and those in the Control group ($F = 98.28$, $df = 2/81$, $P < 0.01$). Nevertheless “DO IT” Creativity proved to be more effective with adjusted Y-mean scores ($X = 62.65$, 77.06 and 72.15) with the overall X-mean of 46.04 compared to the Emotional Mastery with adjusted Y-means ($X = 55.01$, 62.80 and 65.99). Therefore, the sub-hypothesis is also rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Results in tables 1-3 indicated that significant differences existed in the Creativity Motivation scores of treated participants and participants in the control group. The adjusted Y-mean scores revealed that participants exposed to “DO IT” Creativity scored the highest, followed by participants exposed to Emotional Mastery, while participants in the control group came last. This shows that as far as differential effectiveness is concerned, “DO IT” Creativity is more effective than Emotional Mastery in the experimental groups, though Emotional Mastery too is effective. It could be noted that the difference that existed between the treated groups and the control was due to the effects of treatment training programmes. Hence it could be established that “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery Strategies are effective in improving creativity motivation of the participants.

This finding support earlier submissions of Akinboye (1976b), Owolabi (1988), Olagunju (1990) and Animasahun (2002) that creativity motivation could be fostered. However, this is incongruent with Fleith, Rodnigues, Viana and Cerqueira (2000) who postulated that creativity cannot be taught but learned, and “error” is regarded as a potential way to generate creative ideas. Foo (1988) also supported the earlier submission when he reported that creativity education has been an inspiration to educators and leaders in Singapore. Stenberg and Frensch (1993) supported the idea that information obtained during Creativity training session is applicable across a variety of problems.

Participants in the “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery groups might have performed so well on Creativity Motivation variable because of the sensitivity of the programmes, the commitment of the researcher, the motivation or incentives they usually received every session and the cooperation of staff members of the institutions. The fact that the participants were motivated from the beginning to the end of the programme might account for their full commitment and excellent performance.

The evident improvement in creativity motivation of the treated participants would enable them see life problems as challenges that would provoke in them creative thinking, creative solution and higher performance. The study has therefore established that the two treatment strategies (“DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery) are effective in fostering life skills in the treated participants. However, “DO IT” creativity is more effective than Emotional Mastery.

Conclusion

Over the years, persons with physical disabilities have contented themselves with back-bench and second-class status in our society. But this empirical study has shown that they have innate abilities and could excel in self-management, productivity and creativity. Hence the days of self-pity, inferiority complex and dormancy are over. It is high time persons with disabilities took their destiny in their own hands with appropriate life skills and march forward in the drama of survival and healthy competition in our society. Indeed, more than anything else, it is these life skills which persons with disabilities require most to be able to survive at home, at school, at work, in leisure, in marriage, and in their relationships with others in society.

The findings in this study have shown that both “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery were veritable intervention programmes in improving creativity motivation and emotional intelligence as well as reducing the inferiority complex, dormancy and lack of productivity of adolescents with special needs in Oyo State, Nigeria. The two strategies were effective in fostering life skills in the participants, though “DO IT” Creativity is more effective than Emotional Mastery. Furthermore, participants in the experimental groups performed significantly higher than those in the control group which indicates that the treatment strategies were very effective.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in the study, the following are the recommendations:

1. “DO IT” Creativity strategy should be employed to foster creativity motivation among adolescents with special needs and their able-bodied counterparts.
2. Emotional Mastery technique should be used to nurture creativity motivation among persons with special needs and their able-bodied counterparts.
3. A combination of “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery should be employed to produce greater improvement in creativity motivation among persons with special needs and their able-bodied counterparts.
4. A combination of “DO IT” Creativity and Emotional Mastery should be employed to foster creativity motivation across the strata of learners’ population.
5. An appropriate legislation should be put in place to enrich quality of life of persons with special needs.

Educational Implications

The findings of this study were quite important and relevant to the current educational focus on creativity, innovation, resourcefulness, entrepreneurship and self-employment of graduates (school leavers). The integration of creativity motivation in the curricula of schools, colleges, polytechnics and universities would catapult the nation to greatness at lesser cost within a short period of time.

Ethical Consideration

The study abided by ethical guidelines in terms of voluntary participation, safety and confidentiality of the participants. Approval and cooperation of all the institutions used were secured. All the data obtained were anonymized to protect the privacy of the participants, and also showcased the integrity of the investigators. The participants were initially informed about their right to withdraw themselves from the study at any point without any consequence.

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